

EXPLORING THE PRACTICAL USE OF A COLLABORATIVE ROBOT FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a set of experiences related to the setup and exploration of potential educational uses of a collaborative robot (cobot).

The basic principles that have guided the work carried out have been three. First and foremost, study of all the functionalities offered by the robot and exploration of its potential academic uses both in subjects focused on industrial robotics and in subjects of related disciplines (automation, communications, computer vision). Second, achieve the total integration of the cobot at the laboratory, seeking not only independent uses of it but also seeking for applications (laboratory practices) in which the cobot interacts with some of the other devices already existing at the laboratory (other industrial robots and a flexible manufacturing system). Third, reuse of some

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available components and minimization of the number and associated cost of required new components.

The experiences, carried out following a project-based learning methodology under the framework of bachelor and master subjects and thesis, have focused on the integration of mechanical, electronic and programming aspects in new design solutions (end effector, cooperative workspace, artificial vision system integration) and case studies (advanced task programming, cybersecure communication, remote access).

These experiences have consolidated the students' acquisition of skills in the transition to professional life by having the close collaboration of the university faculty with the experts of the robotics company.

1 INTRODUCTION

A collaborative robot (cobot) is an example of an industrial robot in which, basically, the measurement of force in the end effector and mechanical joints has been added to the traditional way of controlling the position and speed of the end effector in order to sometimes allow the physical contact with the human operator. A second characteristic is the elimination of the physical barrier between the cobot and the operator: through sensors and programming, the approach of the operator to the cobot translates into a reduction in the speed of the cobot and even its stoppage [1]. A third characteristic is the flexibility of the cobot's tasks, in the context of cooperation between the cobot and the operator, which allows a cobot to be started up accompanying the operator in jobs in small and medium-sized companies in tasks that were initially carried out manually (assembly).

As can be seen in the previous paragraph, one of the challenges in the implementation of tasks and processes in which the cobot and the human combine their skills to improve performance. The cobot can be useful both at the organizational level of the company and at the level of interaction with the operator [2]. In this last aspect, a cobot oriented to access and use by a human operator must allow various operators with different training to develop skills, or perfect existing ones for an effective teamwork.

It is necessary to address the practical use of cobots in higher education for various reasons, including:

- a) current manufacturing processes are in transition towards a connected industry (industry 4.0) in which collaborative robotics is included as an emerging technology [3]
- b) the improvement of the functionality of the cobot through programming algorithms (basic task programming, recursive programming, programming using artificial intelligence algorithms) can transform the cobot in the direction of a cognitive robot in a few years [4]

Higher education must accompany the engineering student in this adaptation. This requires changes in the engineering curriculum [5], specifically the inclusion of

collaborative robotics concepts in industrial robotics subjects, the creation of laboratory practices with cobots, and the development of final degree projects.

The Section two explains the methodology developed, paying attention to the relationship between different users. The section three explain in more detail the effectiveness of this approach in the development of three case studies. Finally, conclusions are future steps are presented.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this work is project-based learning. The methodology has been adapted to three scenarios:

- a) Subject within an engineering degree
- b) Final degree project
- c) Life-long learning

The agents involved in this methodology are:

- a) Teachers of various subjects
- b) Teachers and experts from robotics companies
- c) Teachers, laboratory maintenance staff, final degree students

2.1 Subject

There are two subjects, Industrial Robotics and Computer Vision (RIVC) and Integration of Automatic Systems (ISA) that use the same laboratory resources. The first one divided in two parts show industrial robotics and the relationship with computer vision (2 h in laboratory each week, 14 th weeks). The second subject is a project oriented subject (3h in laboratory each week, 14 th weeks), with the aim to encourage students to the development of final projects in automation. Both subjects share in the experimental part the need to consolidate teamwork skills.

2.2 Final degree project

Some final degree projects have been proposed and developed [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], all of them oriented towards the integration of a collaborative robot UR3e [11] in the laboratory: development of electronic prototypes, design and programming of robotic applications. The main aim is to reduce the gap between undergraduate engineering students and professionals in electronics and automation companies. The first final degree project related to the start up of the cobot in the laboratory (two months) allowed the robot station to be shown at an open session for future engineering students (february 2020) at the hall of our school. Finally, the student published an article into an Spanish Journal as a first author [12].

2.3 Life-long learning

In this aspect, collaboration between the University and robotics companies is being promoted. Some students carry out internships and final degree projects in companies with the advice of the teaching staff.

The teaching staff provides students with the possibility of attending an annual fair (Advanced Factories) with the latest developments in industry 4.0. Students are asked

to attend, meet with business experts and prepare a small document with a list of companies and future job opportunities.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Electrical gripper

The end effector is the device that, mounted on the end of the robot (or cobot) arm, allows it to perform a certain task. There are two main categories of end effectors, grippers that allow the manipulation of objects, and specific tools that allow implementing tasks such as welding, painting, etc. In academic environments, it is common to illustrate the use of robots and cobots mainly in tasks that involve the manipulation of small objects. According to this, the most commonly used type of gripper are electrical grippers.

When thinking about equipping the collaborative robot with a gripper, multiple commercial models available on the market could have been compared and one of them could have been purchased and installed on the cobot. This would have been a quick and easy solution, but it would also have been expensive. And, perhaps more important, very little would have been learned from the process. That is why, instead of acquiring a commercial gripper, the design and prototyping of it from scratch was considered as an alternative and a final degree project with this goal was proposed [10]. This option is viable, since the challenge is within the reach of students who are finishing the degree in Industrial Electronics and Automation and since the necessary means are available at the school. In addition, it is an option that has its advantages, the main ones being that both the student and the supervisor (teacher) acquire new knowledge and that the obtained product has a much lower cost than its commercial equivalent.

Taking previous considerations into account, and using as reference the basic models of adaptive electric grippers commercialized by some of the most important manufacturers (Schunk, Robotiq and OnRobot), a 2-finger parallel gripper with electrical actuation has been designed. The mechanical design is simple and it can be easily implemented with conventional 3D printing equipment. The actuation and control are based on the use and programming of a Dynamixel AX-12A servo motor and an Arduino Nano board. The result is a gripper with a maximum opening of 80mm, which allows handling objects of up to 1kg and with an opening/closing time of less than 1 second. These characteristics are comparable to those of simple commercial pliers, but obtained at a much lower economic cost: the total cost of the prototype remains around 100 euros, while a comparable commercial model can be around 1,000 euros. All the details about the mechanical, electrical and electronic design of this gripper can be found in [10].

Figure 1 shows the first prototype of the gripper. This prototype has already been installed in the cobot. It works correctly and it is going to be used extensively. Additionally, according to available economic resources and opportunities, more collaborative robots will be acquired and new copies of the gripper will be manufactured and installed with reduced effort and cost.

Fig. 1. First prototype of the 2-finger parallel gripper.

3.2 Workpiece classification using computer vision

Another relevant result of the work carried out so far has been the implementation of a complete example that combines the use of collaborative robotics with computer vision [8].

In this example, the objective is to classify objects of different types and colours that at the beginning are randomly distributed in a given area close to the robot. To do this, an artificial vision system must identify the type and location of the different objects and provide this information to the cobot. At the left side of Figure 2, a photo of the whole system is presented, where the initial zone and the destination zones and containers can be observed.

Fig. 2. Workpiece classification system: (left) whole system; (right) detail of the integrated vision system.

For the development of this example, and again following the principle that designing from scratch is much more educational and cheaper than acquiring commercial devices (the cost of an industrial vision system is also in the range of a few thousand euros), a vision system based on a Raspberry Pi and a Pi camera has been designed

and integrated into the robot. The choice of the Raspberry is motivated by its small size, its low cost (not only for the Raspberry but also for the camera) and for the possibility of using a standard environment for the development of computer vision applications: Python (programming language) + Open CV (Computer Vision library). The system has been mounted on an end effector with two pneumatic grippers (which was acquired just after the cobot and before designing and prototyping the electric gripper presented in the previous section), using a custom case with a fixation system that has been manufactured using 3D printing. Communication between the Raspberry Pi and the UR3e controller is established using the Ethernet ports available on both devices. In Figure 2, at the right, a photo of the vision system after installation is shown.

The scope and complexity of this example makes it suitable to be used, under a PBL (Project Based Learning) methodology, as a project to be solved in the Industrial Robotics and Computer Vision subject, an idea that will be put into practice starting the next academic course.

The resolution of the project will be planned according to the four fundamental problems to be solved: recognition and location of objects; transformation of image coordinates to robot coordinates; Raspberry-UR3e communication; manipulation by the robot. The solution of these four problems will go through the programming of both the Raspberry and the UR3e. In principle, all the work groups established in class will have to solve the same project (which accepts different types of solutions), but if considered pertinent, different variants may be established, such as those that may result from considering different sets of object types.

3.3 RoboDK tutorials and exercises

Both in industry and in academic environments, off-line programming and robot simulation environments are useful. In an industrial context, this type of software tools allow programs to be developed and simulated before testing them on real robots that must finally execute them. In addition, in an academic context, the availability of simulators makes it possible to have more working groups (pairs of students) in the laboratory than the number of real robots available (in the Industrial Automation and Robotics laboratory there are eight working places equipped with PCs + programming and simulation software, while there are only three robots, two conventional industrial robots plus the new collaborative robot; each group of students spends a good part of the time at their working place and they only use one of the robots to do the final tests).

RoboDK is an off-line programming and simulation software [13]. As a programming environment, it allows robots to program robots of different manufacturers by using a same high-level graphical language (this is a double advantage since the graphic language is easier to use and it is also universal and independent of proprietary language of each manufacturer). As a simulation environment, it allows programs to be tested independently of the fact that they can later also be tested on the real robot. As a whole, it can be useful both in laboratory sessions and in theory sessions to be able to illustrate many concepts.

Fig. 3. Assembly example in RoboDK.

Given the potential educational utility of RoboDK, its study was proposed as part of a final degree project [9]. The result of this work was a set of basic tutorials and a set of programming and simulation exercises with different levels of difficulty (all of them documented and resolved). Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the solution of an exercise in which it is requested to program and simulate an assembly task.

Unlike the electric gripper and the parts classification system, which have not yet been used within the framework of laboratory practices of any subject, RoboDK tutorials and practices have already been used during the academic year 2021- 2022 in the subject Integration of Automatic Systems.

Thus, in the recent edition of this subject, the students enrolled (12) have carried out two 3-hour laboratory sessions about the use of the simulator and a third 3-hour laboratory session about the use of the real cobot. After these sessions, the students answered a System Usability Scale (SUS) satisfaction questionnaire with scale 0-100, obtaining a mean value of 61.2 and a standard deviation of 19.4 [14]. Figure 4 shows the response to question 5 "I found the various features of the tutorial to be fairly well integrated", Likert scale 4 strongly agree, 0 strongly disagree.

Fig. 4. Answers to question 5 of the SUS questionnaire.

In this questionnaire, the students emphasize that the 3D simulator is easy to learn and use, although the quality of the tutorials must continue to be improved, since the 3D simulator interface is apparently in graphic format, while the advanced functionalities are in text format and it uses Python programming, so learning the simulator is not so easy.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This article shows how to promote the development of projects in industrial robotics in the teaching laboratory, achieving integration with the rest of the equipment and facilitating the learning and skills of undergraduate engineering students.

Taking into account the projects already developed, the next steps are in the direction of add a second robot and develop collaborative task between students and robots, measuring in more detail the satisfaction of the students with this approach and promoting innovation projects (design of a sensitive gripper, use of OPC UA communications in collaborative robotics).

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